

Research Article

Exploring The Determinants of Married Employee Attrition: A Logistic Regression

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Abstract: This study investigates the determinants of employee attrition among married employees using logistic regression analysis. Employee attrition poses significant organizational productivity and growth challenges, particularly among married individuals who balance professional and personal responsibilities. The research aims to identify the determinants influencing attrition, including demographic, organizational, and job satisfaction elements, and to predict the likelihood of employee attrition based on these predictors. A dataset from the Kaggle website was used, which involved 366 married employees. The study applies logistic regression to evaluate the significance of variables such as gender, distance from home, work-life balance, and job satisfaction. Logistic regression results indicate that gender, poor work-life balance, and moderate job satisfaction contribute significantly to attrition, while factors such as age and income show minimal influence. These results were supported by *p*-values under the standard threshold of 0.05, highlighting their significance in affecting employees' likelihood of departing from the organization. The predictive efficiency of the model was checked using measures such as Cox and Snell's R^2 and Nagelkerke's R^2 , which showed the model was good at explaining a lot of the reasons for leaving. Overall, significant predictors like gender, distance from home, and work-life balance play a crucial role in attrition, while trivial factors such as age and monthly income have little impact. These findings emphasize prioritizing relevant variables to better understand and model attrition dynamics.

Keywords: employee attrition; married employees; logistic regression; job satisfaction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Employee attrition is typically categorized into four types which are voluntary attrition, involuntary attrition, compulsory attrition, and natural attrition (Negi, 2013). These categories help organizations identify the underlying causes of employee attrition and design effective solutions to reduce attrition and boost employee retention.

Employee attrition, a major challenge for organizations globally, is the phenomenon of employees leaving the company for a variety of reasons. This issue has a negative effect on long-term growth objectives and workplace productivity; thus, organizations must address it effectively (Alqahtani et al., 2024). Besides, this study aims to investigate the factors contributing to attrition among married employees.

Figure 1. Employees Who Intend to Leave Their Current Job within 12 Months

Figure 1 shows a bar graph by Teo (n.d.). The bar chart describes the employee’s attrition in different regions. It indicates that Australia and New Zealand are at high risk of losing employees with a rate of 23 percent. Organizations should adopt a proactive approach to fight employee attrition by identifying the main causes that create attrition and applying certain retention strategies (Setiawan et al., 2020). These measures may involve offering attractive salaries and benefits, creating avenues for career growth, cultivating a supportive work environment, and encouraging a healthy work-life balance (Khan, 2019).

According to the findings from Chen (2023), married employees are the second to experience higher levels of attrition after single employees. This study used logistic regression to analyze employee data and identify the factors that will increase the likelihood of married employees leaving their jobs. In this study, factors such as excessive workload, limited career advancement, strained interpersonal relationships, emotional labor, work-life conflicts, and interference with personal life are examined. Another study by Haldorai et al. (2019) on the hotel sector in Malaysia revealed similar findings: that many issues such as inadequate compensation, excessive working hours, overwhelming workload, limited opportunities for career growth, strained interpersonal relationships, emotional demands of the job, and conflicts between work and home life, strongly influenced the likelihood of hotel employees wanting to leave their jobs.

In conclusion, the majority of the research reveals that work-related stress, work-life imbalance, and pull factors, including a lack of career progression and an unpleasant work environment, increase married employee attrition. So, the primary focus of this study will be on married individuals who have made the risky decision to leave their jobs since marriage is a critical aspect of life, involving numerous responsibilities. The objectives of this study are to 1) To determine the most significant factors that contribute to married employees’ attrition within an organization, 2) To predict the likelihood of a married employee leaving the organization based on various predictor variables.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This secondary data aims to analyze married employee attrition and its associated factors using the dataset “Employee Attrition and Factors” from the Kaggle website. The variables selected for analysis include attrition (specifically focusing on married individuals), age, gender, total working

years, monthly income, distance from home, work-life balance and job satisfaction. This study only analyze attrition among married employees, hence examining a randomly selected sample of 366 from the total 7511 cases of married employees. Using logistic regression enables a more rigorous examination of the relationships of different predictor variables to the likelihood of jobs departure for married employees and provides important insights into the multi variable interplay of factors that influence whether married employees leave their jobs. To differentiate our study from previous research, we will focus on a distinct aspect of employee attrition among married.

Figure 2. Theoretical Framework of Employee Attrition Determinants

Figure 2 above shows the theoretical framework of this study. There are 7 independent variables which are age (X1), gender (X2), total working years (X3), monthly income (X4), distance from home (X5), work-life balance (X6), job satisfaction (X7) while attrition rate among employees is denoted as the dependent variable, y which is 0 = stayed (in terms of not leaving the organization) and 1 = left (in terms of leaving the organization).

3. FINDINGS

In this study, age, distance from home, monthly income, total working years are continuous variables while gender, job satisfaction, work-life balance are categorical predictor variables. The response is defined as y = 1 or y = 0, which is known as a dichotomous result, with y = 1 indicating the occurrence of the event. In this study, attrition = 1 represents married people who left the organizations, whereas attrition = 0 represents married people who stayed. The model was developed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26.

The logistic regression equation is expressed as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = -0.032 - 0.012X_1 + 1.000X_2 + 0.003X_3 + 0.000X_4 + 0.011X_5 + 1.535X_6 + 0.878X_7 - 0.256X_8 + 0.261X_9 - 0.925X_{10} - 0.602X_{11}$$

where

X₁ = Age,

X₂ = Gender (1 = Female, 0 = Male),

- X₃ = Total Working Years,
- X₄ = Monthly Income,
- X₅ = Distance from Home,
- X₆ =Work-Life Balance (1 = Poor, 0 = Others),
- X₇ =Work-Life Balance (1 = Fair, 0 = Others),
- X₈ =Work-life Balance (1 = Good, 0 = Others),
- X₉ = Job Satisfaction (1 = Low, 0 = Others),
- X₁₀ = Job Satisfaction (1 = Medium, 0 = Others),
- X₁₁ = Job Satisfaction (1 = High, 0 = Others).

Several predictors were included in the analysis from the table of variables, with dummy variables having been created for categorical predictors such as work-life balance (WLB) and job satisfaction. 'Excellent' was the reference category for work-life balance and 'very high' for job satisfaction. Eleven variables were analyzed and categorical variables were encoded as dummy variables so that it was compatible with the regression model. This approach provides a more detailed assessment of the relationships between these predictors and the outcome.

Based on the Omnibus test of model coefficients, the logistic regression model is overall statistically significant with Chi-Square value of 69.357 and p-value is 0.000. Meanwhile, the Hosmer and Lemeshow Test showed that result of married employee attrition supports the validity of the model for understanding the relationship between the continuous predictors (age, years at the company, monthly income, and distance from home) and attrition.

3.1 Wald Statistics

The Wald statistic evaluates the impact of individual predictors like age, gender, total working years, monthly income, distance from home, work-life balance and job satisfaction on the logistic regression model, determining their contribution to attrition as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables in the Equation

Variables	Name	Wald	Sig.
Constant	Attrition	0.002	0.964
X ₁	Age	1.167	0.280
X ₂	Gender (Female)	17.903	0.000
X ₃	Total Working Years	0.053	0.818
X ₄	Monthly Income	2.593	0.107
X ₅	Distance from Home	7.007	0.008
X ₆	Work-Life Balance (Poor)	11.528	0.001
X ₇	Work-Life Balance (Fair)	6.195	0.013
X ₈	Work-Life Balance (Good)	0.491	0.484
X ₉	Job Satisfaction (Low)	0.332	0.565
X ₁₀	Job Satisfaction (Medium)	6.140	0.013
X ₁₁	Job Satisfaction (High)	4.232	0.040

The null hypothesis (H₀) states that the independent variable has no significant effect on attrition, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) suggests a significant effect. Based on Wald statistics in Table 1, predictors such as Gender (p = 0.000), Distance from Home (p = 0.008), Poor and Fair Work-Life Balance (p = 0.001 and 0.013) and Medium and High Job Satisfaction (p = 0.013 and 0.040) are statistically significant, with p-values below 0.05. This indicates their strong influence on attrition.

In contrast, variables such as Age (p = 0.280), Years at Company (p = 0.818), Monthly Income (p = 0.107), Good Work-Life Balance (p = 0.484), and Low Job Satisfaction (p = 0.565) are statistically

insignificant, as their p-values exceed 0.05. These factors do not meaningfully contribute to explaining attrition in this study. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of key predictors like Gender and Work-Life Balance while suggesting the removal of less relevant variables to improve the model's efficiency.

3.2 Predictive Efficiency Model

The predictive efficiency of a model is its ability to accurately classify or predict events based on provided predictors. In logistic regression, it distinguishes between attrition and non-attrition outcomes using metrics like accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and AUC. The results are shown in table 2 below.

Table 2. Classification Table

Predicted	Attrition		Percentage Correct
	0	1	
0 (Stayed)	127	56	69.4
1 (Left)	63	120	65.6
Overall Percentage			67.5

Table 2 shows the classification table that provides a breakdown of how accurately the logistic regression model predicted employee attrition. The model correctly predicted 67.5 percent of the cases overall. Specifically, it correctly identified 69.4 percent of employees who did not leave the company (true negatives) and 65.6 percent of employees who did leave (true positives). This indicates that the model is relatively good at identifying married employee attrition. However, it misclassified the remaining 30.6 percent of employees who did not leave as leaving (false positives) and 34.4 percent of employees who did leave as staying (false negatives).

Meanwhile, the Cox and Snell R Square value of 0.173 indicates that approximately 17.3 percent of the variation in attrition can be explained by the predictors included in the logistic regression model. However, because the Cox and Snell R Square does not reach the maximum possible value of 1.0 in logistic regression, it may underestimate the explained variance. The Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.230 adjusts the Cox and Snell value to provide a more accurate measure, showing that about 23.0 percent of the variability in attrition is accounted for by the model. This suggests that while the predictors have a moderate ability to explain attrition, there is still substantial unexplained variability, indicating the need for further exploration or inclusion of additional predictors to improve the model's explanatory power.

4. DISCUSSION

The results revealed that gender, distance from home, work-life balance (WLB) categories and job satisfaction levels were all significant predictors of attrition. Findings from Pallathadka et al. (2022) and Dagar and Kapur (2020) also indicate that gender plays a role and gender-based issues. For example, work-life balance and workplace culture are major factors that influence attrition rates. Distance from home was also a strong predictor, which aligns with Khera and Divya (2018) who found that employee who live farther away from the workplace are more likely to leave their jobs. These results suggest that geographic factors substantially affect employees' decision to stay or leave.

Work-life balance also plays a crucial role, as employees with poor or fair balance are more likely to leave, reflected by high odds ratios for work-life balance in poor category or denoted as WLB Poor (4.641) and work-life balance in fair category, WLB Fair (2.406). The literature is verified with Chenshu et al. (2024) and Zainal et al. (2022) emphasizing that poor work-life balance contributes to

increased attrition rates, while a balanced environment enhances retention. Regarding job satisfaction, this study found that levels such as 'Medium' and 'High' significantly affect attrition, aligning with Muda et al. (2022) and Kabungaidze et al. (2013), who noted that dissatisfaction drives attrition, whereas higher satisfaction reduces it.

Conversely, variables such as age, total working years, and job satisfaction (low) were found to be statistically insignificant. This is somewhat surprising, as the previous study by Kanchana and Jayathilaka (2023) and Yang and Islam (2020) highlighted age as an influential factor, particularly for younger employees. However, the insignificant effect of low job satisfaction aligns with findings from Rajasekar and Prasad (2017), job satisfaction may be high, yet stress can still cause employee attrition. Chen (2023)'s study (2023) suggested that longer employment duration significantly influences employee attrition with older workers being less likely to leave their jobs due to their emotional investment in their work which are differ from the result of this study. These variations highlight how context-specific attrition predictors are and how crucial it is to comprehend organizational details when creating retention plans.

The study also noted that monthly household income is an important determinant, following the literature by Hasan and Pandey (2018) stated that employees who earn less tend to have higher attrition rates. Nevertheless, it is not always directly proportional as Rao et al. (2024) asserted that both low-earning and high-wage earners are likely to leave more than the middle-earners. This implies that financial incentives must be carefully adjusted to meet the various needs of employees from all economic levels.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, both objectives were achieved successfully. The first objective is to determine the most significant factors contributing to employee attrition, revealing multiple predictors with a substantial correlation to attrition. Key factors such as gender, how far they live from home, work-life balance (categorized as 'poor' and 'fair') and job satisfaction (categorized as 'medium' and 'high') were major reasons for leaving an organization. These results were supported by p-values under the standard threshold of 0.05, highlighting their significance in affecting employees' likelihood to depart from the organization.

The second objective is to predict the likelihood of employee attrition based on various predictor variables, was also done by logistic regression modeling. The predictive efficiency of the model was checked using measures such as Cox and Snell's R^2 and Nagelkerke's R^2 , which showed the model was good at explaining a lot of the reasons for leaving.

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